

Critical Review On Insufficient Supply Of Milk During Breast Feeding And Its Consequences

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Abstract

Breastfeed is the first right of baby. Mothers have to feed baby within first hour of birth of baby and then continue till six months as exclusive breastfeed. It has got so many useful benefits for both baby and mother in future. But it may not be possible for some of the mother to supply sufficient milk to satisfy the hunger to get proper nutrition to infants. In that case it is critical situations for both mother and baby. During breastfeed prolactin and oxytocin hormones is released. Oxytocin makes mother feel relax, peaceful and just keep eye on her child. It also creates perfect bond of love between mother and child. The main function of prolactin is to make milk for breastfeed after birth. So there are lots of benefits from breastfeeding. Insufficient supply of milk will lead to have many issues such as health complication to mother and child and it will effect whole family, whole nation, and ultimately whole world. The cause of insufficient supply must be searched out and proper solution should be done in practice.

Keywords

Prolactin, Oxytocin, Insufficient Breastmilk.

Introduction

Breast milk is very useful and amazing nutritious supply provided by mother to baby. But unfortunately many mothers are not able to feed baby sufficiently. Studies show that there are many reasons behind this. When there is less supply of milk then there is obstacle in feeding occurs. Complications such as obesity, thyroid and diabetes may cause insufficient supply of milk. If the mother is not able to feed then she has to rely on donor milk. One such donor milk is called formula milk. The main reason behind introduction of commercial formula milk is due to insufficient supply of breast milk. Mother's milk was not enough to meet the nutritional requirements of infants. It is international and national priority for the exclusive breast feeding duration to be improved. Health workers, Researchers, Nutritionist and Government will have to play a great role in framing policies regarding to solve this obstacles of mother's milk supply.

Objective of study

The paper is based on the critical review on insufficient supply of milk during breast feeding and its consequences.

Review of Literature

This is a review based paper hence all the latest reviews have been discussed through out the paper.

Main Text

Reasons related to insufficient supply of breast milk

Perception of insufficient milk: Many studies revealed that mothers perceive that infants are dissatisfied with the feed due to insufficient supply of milk. But actually researchers, clinicians, and mothers do not evaluate the supply of milk in actual figure. Maternal education is required to assess the milk supply (Lisa Gatti.2008)

Main factors: Researchers showed that initiations of delayed breastfeeding and having little knowledge regarding exclusive breast feeding are the main factors for perception of insufficient supply of milk (Yi Huang, Yu Liu 2021).

Several issues are there for less breast milk production:

1. Health issue such as Hormone imbalance, if there is any disturbance in prolactin and oxytocin than the supply of breast milk will be low.
2. Gastric surgery.
3. Medications,
4. Poor nutrition, Breast milk require optimum nutrition enzymes, antibodies for frequent supply of milk, if there is any hinderance or lacking than the milk supply will be low.
5. High stress are the reasons for less milk production (Jenna Marburger. 2022).

Insufficient breastmilk: It may lead to nutritional deficiencies, hypoglycemia, hypernatremia and failure to grow well in infants (Olivia Piccolo et al.2022). Infants who

get sufficient mothers milk are having more IQ as compared to those who are having insufficient mothers milk observed by many researchers.

Low income: It has been seen in a study that insufficient supply of breastmilk is more common in low and middle income group mothers (Desai et al'2014) as compared to mothers with high income group and low income group mothers are at more risk of getting stress due to lack of resources and hence the reason of insufficient human milk (Witten C et al.2020).

Alternate method: Inadequate milk production give rise to use alternate method such as formula milk and weaning practices (Nkoka O et al. 2019, Kent JC et al. 2011, Gardner H et al.2016). Alternate method cannot replace mother's milk.

Some maternal cause of insufficiencies: It has been seen in many studies that insufficient milk production may be due to mammary tissue may not be in appropriate condition. Neurological pathways may be not in proper ways to carry out function in the body. Ductal system in disturbed condition in the body which will hamper the function of organ in the body to discharge milk. Abnormal functions of hormones such as insulin, oestrogen, progesterone, prolactin, oxytocin and growth hormone will lead to insufficient milk production.(Wight N, Marinelli KA. 2014).

Malnutrition: Overnutrition and undernutrition comes under malnutrition but mostly the undernutrition type of malnutrition which include less quantity of protein, energy and other essential nutrients intake cause insufficient breast milk supply. It has been seen in a study that high level of undernutrition is found in low income mother (Victoria et al. 2008). The quality and quantity of breast milk is influenced by malnourished mothers and this is going to influence their offspring.

Maternal education: In different studies it has been seen that mothers who are well educated are able to breastfeed more successfully rather than less educated (Tang W K, et al.2019, Acharya P et al.2015, Mogre V.et al.2016).

Impact of caesarean: It has been observed in a study that failure to breast feeding is more in mothers who have gone through caesarean rather than who have vaginal delivery (Hobbs AJ, et al. 2016). It may also be due to sitting position during breastfeeding.

Psychological effect: Insufficient mother's milk production may be due to psychological effect such as unemployment, career, and low income of mothers (Kitano N et al. 2016).

Misconception about urination and defecation: It has been observed in some studies that mothers have misconception that frequent urination and defecation cause infant to have empty stomach, but actually frequent urination and defecation shows sufficient milk rather than insufficient milk(Ministry of Health. 2020, Adequate breastfeeding 2020). Also stool passing is normal phenomena(Diarrhoea in infants.2020 May 24.Medline Plus, U.S. National Library)

Bottle feeding should be avoided: Bottle feeding has many ill affects still mothers feed their infants with bottle. So this type of practices should be avoided and essentially mentioned in health education programme.(Li R, et al. 2014).

Consequences:

It has been seen in many studies that if the babies are not fed mothers milk than they have high risk of getting infectious disease, otitis media, morbidity, and sudden infant death syndrome. Mothers are also likely to have breast cancer, ovarian cancer, type 2 diabetes in case of not breastfeeding their infants (A Stuebe 2009).

Conclusion

Thus it is concluded that there are many obstacles that prevent mothers from breastfeeding. One reason might be low income group mothers do not have high quality of proper balanced diet so that secretion of milk be optimum for baby. Likewise there are so many other reasons for insufficiencies such as impact of caesarean, unemployment, career tensions. So, mothers should be guided properly regarding breastfeeding that in spite of having all obstacles mothers prime duty and responsibility is to feed their baby properly because the babies are their valuable assets. They are the future of the nation. Failure to breastfeeding is harmful to both mothers and infants. Hence, breastfeeding should be promoted.

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